

Stationary Path in a Lagrangian and Energy Conservation

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 8, 2022

In a previous note (1) we argued that variational principles in physics such as Fermat's principle for light or Maupertuis' for particles or maximization of entropy subject to a constant energy in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas follow from a conservation equation. In other words this conservation equation may be transformed into a variational formalism. Furthermore the variational principle is linked with global ideas such as the extremization of total time in Fermat's principle whereas the associated conserved quantity i.e. momentum in the x direction (if the mirror or medium surface is in the x direction) is local. Thus light in such problems moves such that (p_x) is constant and one does not need to worry about how the system senses the overall times of different paths considered in the variational problem.

A typical Lagrangian problem which uses the Lagrangian $L = T - V$ where $T = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $V(x)$ without constraints leads to the differential equation: $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{dL}{dv} - \frac{dL}{dx} = 0$ ((1)). The idea is that many different paths linking two endpoints are considered, but only a stationary path (one which keeps $\int dt L$ stationary) is chosen as the unique solution. The differential equation ((1)) is also equivalent to Newton's second law. Newton's second law, however, is equivalent to a conservation equation for a conservative potential i.e. $\frac{1}{2}mv^2 + V(x) = E$ ((2)) where E is conserved energy at each x, t . Thus the stationary solution from Lagrange's approach (i.e. the solution of ((1))) should also be the solution which conserves energy locally. Given that ((1)) is in the form of Newton's second law i.e. $-dV/dx$, one does not usually think in terms of a conserved energy when solving ((1)).

In this note we ask how the somewhat unusual approach of testing different paths $x(i)(t)$ where i denotes a path such that the initial and final endpoints are the same is linked to conservation of energy. We argue that although the conservation of energy equation ((2)) only contains x , one may link x, t through $x(t)$. Thus changing x to $x+dx$ leaving t constant may be thought of as changing a path. Thus taking a d/dx derivative of ((2)), the conservation of energy equation, may be thought of as finding an equation linked to varying a path. Thus varying paths to find a stationary path is really the same as taking d/dx of the conservation equation and the stationary path is one which conserves energy locally. In other words, the system does not need to somehow sample different paths to find the stationary one, it just needs to evolve with constant energy.

Variational Principles and Global View/ Fermat's and Maupertuis' Principles and Maximization of Entropy

Variational principles are often used because of their computational convenience, but their ideology seems to be linked to global rather than local behaviour. For example, Fermat's least time principle for light extremizes the overall amount of time for light reflecting or refracting. This immediately begs the question: How does the system know globally which path leads to an extremum in overall time? In (1) we argued that extremizing involves taking a derivative which in the reflection/refraction case is linked to an invariant variable. This variable is x if the mirror or medium lies in the x direction at $y=b$. There is a constraint for y , but none for x so it is the

invariant variable. This invariance is directly linked with a conservation law in the same direction namely conservation of (px) i.e. momentum in the x direction. This is a local property i.e. (px) has the same value at $x, x+dx$ etc so one does not need to think globally or ask how it is possible for light to sense the global path which leads to an extremum in overall time.

In (1) we showed that starting with conservation of (px) one may mathematically transform it into two kinds of variational principles. One way leads to Fermat's principle and the other to $-Et+px$.

Similarly maximization of entropy seems to suggest a maximization of all arrangements in a system. One may ask: How does the system know how to do this? We argued, however, that one may consider instead two body elastic reactions which are balanced i.e. $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$ and $n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4)$. Taking \ln of the latter and linking to the former yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. One may then mathematically transform this idea: $\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ into a maximization problem with a constraint: $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$. In other words one multiplies e_i by $n(e_i)$, but then later removes it though $d/dn(e_i)$. Thus one may think in terms of two body collisions instead of an overall global maximization of arrangements, although mathematically the variational approach holds.

Variation in a Lagrangian

For a typical Lagrangian $L=T-V$ where $T=.5mv^2$ and $V(x)$ is a conservative potential and there are no constraints, one may vary: $\int dt L(v,x)$ by considering different paths with the same initial and final endpoints. This leads to the differential equation:

$$d/dt dL/dv - dL/dx = 0 \quad ((1))$$

((1)) yields a solution for a stationary $x(t)$ which chooses the correct unique solution from the various solutions attempted. This is a global approach in principle and begs the question: How does the system know how to test the various different $X(t)$ forms to find the special stationary one $x(t)$?

Conservation of Energy

((1)) is equivalent to Newton's second law with $dL/dx = -Force(x)$. Newton's second law, however, is equivalent to a conservation of energy formalism for conservative potentials i.e.

$$.5mv^2 + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

((1)) is not in the form of a conservation of energy equation and so it seems one does not associate conserved energy with the stationary solution of Lagrange's approach. It seems, however, that a Lagrangian stationary solution must also be the one which conserves energy. Conservation of energy is no longer a global property because the system conserves energy from x to $x+dx$ etc.

The question which arises is: How does conservation of energy lead to the idea of testing different $X(t)$ paths with the same initial and final points to find the stationary one?

If one considers ((2)) then E is a constant which means that $dE/dt = dE/dx = 0$. $V(x)$ however, does not contain time and so taking d/dt would lose all information of $V(x)$. One may note that ((2)) is strictly an equation in x i.e. $v(x)$ and $V(x)$. Nevertheless $x(t)$ so ultimately $v(x) = v(x(t)) = v(t)$. Thus it seems that one may ask the following question: What happens to ((2)) if one considers two different paths: x at t and $x+dx$ at t ? “ t ” does not appear in ((2)) so it seems that one compares ((2)) with x and $x+dx$. Here x at t is the unique solution which conserves energy. The term with $x+dx$, however, leads to the terms equal to taking the derivative d/dx of ((2)). Thus taking d/dx of ((2)) is equivalent to considering a different path from the unique solution $x(t)$. It leads to:

$$M v(x) \frac{d v(x)}{dx} + dV/dx = 0 \quad ((3))$$

Time still does not appear in ((3)), but given that $v=dx/dt$ by definition one may recast ((3)) as:

$$M \frac{d}{dt} v(x) + dV/dx = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial v} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = 0 \quad \text{where } L=T-V \quad ((4))$$

Thus starting with the local idea of conservation of energy and taking d/dx immediately leads to the idea of testing a path different from $x(t)$ and leads to the resulting equation ((4)) which is in the form of a global variational principle which is in fact equivalent to local conservation of energy at each x .

Free Particle Lagrangian

To show how the idea of conservation is key we consider the free particle Action $Lt = \int .5mvv dt$. If one writes $v=x/t$ the $Lt = \int .5mxx/t dt$ or:

$$\int .5mxx/t dt = -Et + px \quad \text{if one writes } t \text{ and } x \text{ on the same footing and considers them independent.}$$

Taking d/dt partial yields: $-.5mxx/tt = -E$ or $T=\text{kinetic energy} = E$ (nonrelativistically)

Taking d/dx partial yields: $mv = p$. Nonrelativistically.

Thus one has conservation of both energy and momentum nonrelativistically.

$$\text{Relativistically: } Lt = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv/cc} = -Et + px$$

Taking d/dt partial yields: $-m_0/\sqrt{1-vv} = -E$ ($c=1$)

Taking d/dx partial yields: $m_0 v/cc / \sqrt{1-vv} = p$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the variational approach of the Lagrangian formalism deals with the idea of comparing $A = \int L dt$ for different paths $X(t)$ with the same initial and final points to find the unique solution $x(t)$ which makes A stationary. This leads to a differential equation $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial v} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = 0$ which is equivalent to Newton's second law. Thus only considering the variational principle one may ask: How is the system able to test all different paths and pick out the one $x(t)$ which is stationary? This question arises because the variational principle deals with global ideas i.e. different overall paths.

One may note, however, that Fermat's principle, a variational principle as well, also deals with the global idea of choosing a path for which overall time is stationary. One may again ask: How is the system able to test different paths and find their overall time values? In (1) we showed that the Fermat's least time principle is equivalent to a local conservation law namely that of momentum in the direction of an invariant spatial variable. This variable is x if the mirror or medium interface lies along x at $y=b$. A conserved (p_x) momentum in the x direction is a local property. Light moves keeping (p_x) constant, but (p_y) receives an abrupt change at the medium interface in the case of refraction. Thus the system does not need to keep track of overall time. Refraction may be described locally using conservation of momentum. Furthermore, one may take the expression of conservation of momentum in the x direction and transform it mathematically to create the form of Fermat's least time principle i.e. a variational principle.

In the case of the Lagrangian we note that the unique stationary solution $x(t)$ must also be the solution which locally conserves energy. The equation: $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial v} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = 0$ is equivalent to Newton's second law, but for a conservative potential this is also equivalent to a conservation of energy equation: $\frac{1}{2}mv^2 + V(x) = E$ ((2)). This equation only contains x , but one may consider a particle to be at x at t or at $x+dx$ at the same t . The second scenario means that the unique solution $x(t)$ is compared with an altered path (the same idea as in the Lagrangian approach). This leads to $\frac{d}{dx}$ of ((2)) or $mv \frac{dv}{dx} + dV/dx = 0$ which may be recast as: $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial v} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = 0$ with $L=T-V$. Thus conservation of energy which is a local property may be recast as an equation comparing $x(t)$ to a varied solution. The stationary solution is one in which E is constant. Thus the underlying idea, we argue, is one of energy conservation. Mathematically this may be transformed into a variational principle which involves global concepts such as comparing different paths with the same initial and final points. That does not mean, it seems, that one must consider that the system globally tests different overall paths. There is an underlying local conservation equation which shows how the system may evolve locally which happens to be mathematically equivalent to a variational principle.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Expressing a Conserved Quantity in Terms of a Derivative to Create a Variational Principle in Physics (preprint, zenodo, 2022)